

**THE HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TURKIC
LANGUAGES AND THE SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THEIR TEACHING**

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Abstract. The article presents the history and stages of the development of the Turkic languages, their historical development, information on learning the Turkic languages, and the specific features of teaching this language.

Key words: Turkic languages, Central Asia, Altai mountains, Orkhon-Yenisei inscriptions, Eastern, North-Eastern, South-Eastern, Western Turkic languages, ancient languages, Chuvash language, manuscript, source.

Turkic languages are a family of languages that are spread across the world and have a common root. They are spoken mainly in Central Asia, the Caucasus, Turkey, the Volga region, Siberia, China, and Eastern Europe. The Turkic language family has an ancient history, and the earliest written sources date back to the Old Turkic scripts and the Orkhon-Yenisei inscriptions. Turkic languages have similarities in phonetics, morphology, and syntax. For example, they use suffixes to create new forms and meanings of words. In addition, word order is usually based on the "possessive-interrogative-complementary" system. Currently, Turkic languages are spoken by approximately 170 million people as a native language, and another 200 million as a second language. The most widespread of these are Turkish, Uzbek, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tatar, Uyghur, and Azerbaijani. Turkic languages are also rich in culture, literature, and historical heritage. Their study plays an important role in understanding historical connections, ethnic associations, and cultural interaction (B.B. Abdushukurov, 2019, 132).

The origins of the Turkic languages date back to ancient times, mainly to the region of Central Asia and the Altai Mountains. According to linguistic and historical research, the Turkic languages are considered part of the Altai language family. This family includes Turkic, Mongolian, and Tungus-Manchu languages, although there are different scientific theories about this relationship (G. Akramov, 1997, 78-81).

The formation of the Turkic languages dates back to approximately the 3rd-2nd millennium BC. The ancient Turkic peoples were nomads, engaged in cattle breeding, and lived in vast territories. The initial form of their language was the same, but over time, differences began to emerge between different tribes and regions. The first written monuments of the Turkic languages are the Orkhan-Yenisei inscriptions dating back to the 6th-8th centuries AD. These monuments used the Old Turkic language, which is the main source for studying the structure, grammar and vocabulary of the language.

The spread of the Turkic languages occurred due to the nomadic life and military expansion of the ancient Turkic tribes. Through the Huns, Western Turks and other tribal unions, the Turkic languages reached Eastern Europe, the Caucasus, and Northern China.

The origin and development of the Turkic languages show that they are closely related not only to linguistic, but also to cultural, historical and political processes.

The Turkic languages are diverse and are divided into several linguistically related groups. The differentiation of these languages is mainly based on phonetic, morphological and lexical similarities. Below we will briefly touch on the main types and groups of Turkic languages:

Eastern Turkic languages.

This group originated from the ancient Uyghur language.

Main representatives: Uyghur language (spoken in the Xinjiang region of China)

Uzbek language (spread in Uzbekistan and neighboring countries. Their characteristics.

The sound system is partially influenced by Persian and Arabic languages.

Northeastern Turkic languages.

Main languages: Yakut language (spoken in Northern Siberia, Russia).

Tuvian language (spread in the Republic of Tyva, Russia).

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Features: Lexical influence of peoples in the cold climate region is observed. Southeastern Turkic languages (Karluk group).

Main languages: Uzbek language (has similarities with the Eastern Turkic languages). Uyghur language. This group was historically widespread in the Charkhitai and Transoxiana regions.

Western Turkic languages (Kipchog group).

Main languages: Kazakh language (in Kazakhstan and neighboring countries).

Kyrgyz language (Kyrgyzstan and Central Asian regions).

Tatar (Tatarstan region of Russia).

Bashkir (in the Republic of Bashkiriya).

Southwestern Turkic languages (Oguz group).

Main languages: Turkish (in Turkey and some parts of Europe).

Azerbaijani (in Azerbaijan and Iran).

Turkmen (Turkmenistan and neighboring regions).

Chuvash language.

This language developed separately from other Turkic languages.

Distributed in the Chuvash Republic and the Volga region.

Historically, it is considered to have originated from the ancient Bulgarian language.

Manuscripts and ancient languages.

Old Turkic language (language of the Orkhon-Yenisei inscriptions).

Khorezmian Turkic language (language of written monuments in the Transoxiana region).

The historical development of Turkic languages goes back a long time and includes many stages. The formation and changes of these languages are mainly associated with historical, social, political and cultural factors. Although Turkic languages have retained their agglutinative structure from ancient times to the

present day, significant changes have been observed in their phonetics, lexicon and grammar (B.B. Abdushukurov, 2019, 132).

The ancient period (3rd century BC - 6th century AD) saw the formation and initial development of the Turkic languages.

The ancient Turkic peoples were nomads and communicated with each other through their own language.

During the Hun Empire, Turkic languages were widespread.

There are almost no written sources from this period, but information about the early forms of the language can be obtained through archaeological and linguistic research.

The ancient Turkic period (6th–10th centuries).

During this period, Turkic languages were recorded through written monuments.

The Orkhon-Yenisei Inscriptions: The first written sources written in the ancient Turkic language, dating back to the 8th century AD.

The Middle Turkic period (10th–16th centuries)

This period was a period of increased influence of Islamic culture in the territories of Transoxiana and Khorezm.

The number of words that entered the Turkic languages from Persian and Arabic increased significantly.

A large number of written works appeared, For example:

Mahmud Kashgari's "Devonu lug'otit-turk" - provides rich information about the vocabulary and grammar of Turkic languages.

Alisher Navoi's works - made a great contribution to the literary development of Turkic languages.

New Turkic era (17th-19th centuries).

During this period, Turkic languages developed in connection with the national formation of peoples. Turkic languages were used as official and communication languages of various states. National languages were formed on

the basis of local dialects: Uzbek, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, etc. Changes led to the formation of new literary languages. New words from Russian and other European languages were added to the language.

Modern era (20th century - present day).

In the 20th century, Turkic languages became an integral part of national statehood and cultural development. During this period, the Latin, Cyrillic and Arabic alphabets were used. Later, national languages were strengthened as state languages.

In the 20th century, the Turkic languages became linguistically and literarily richer. Formalized language rules were developed. New terms related to technology and science entered the language.

One of the largest regions of the Turkic languages. This area is considered the historical homeland of the Turkic peoples. Uzbekistan (Uzbek language), Kazakhstan (Kazakh language), Kyrgyzstan (Kyrgyz language), Turkmenistan (Turkmen language), some regions of Tajikistan (Uzbek language).

Some parts of Mongolia (Tuvinian language).

Another widespread part of the Turks is widespread in Asia Minor, the Near East and Eastern Europe. In Asia Minor, the Ogiz tribe of Turks is mainly widespread

In Eastern Europe, peoples belonging to the Kipchak group mainly live. Territories: Volga region of Russia (Tatar and Bashkir languages). Ukraine (Crimean Tatar language). Balkan regions (Turkic language) (G. Abdurakhmonov, A. Rustamov, 1982, 167).

Other subgroups of Turkic languages, such as Crimean Tatar, Bashkir, Khakass, and Chuvash, have relatively few speakers, but they have retained their cultural and linguistic significance.

Historical influences and reasons for spread The migration of nomadic Turkic tribes over vast territories from ancient times contributed greatly to the spread of languages.

Empires: Turkic languages have been the main language of communication of many states in history (for example, the Chigatai state, the Ottoman Empire).

Cultural influence: Literature, trade and religious teachings contributed to the widespread spread of Turkic languages.

Turkic languages are of great importance not only linguistically, but also in the preservation and dissemination of cultural heritage. These languages have played a key role in the historical, literary and cultural development of the Turkic peoples. The cultural significance of the Turkic languages is highlighted in various aspects below.

Preservation and development of literary heritage.

Ancient written sources.

One of the first written examples of Turkic languages is the Orkhan-Yenisei monuments, which reflect the cultural and social life of the ancient Turkic peoples.

For example; Inscriptions of Bilga Kokand and Kul Tegin.

In the Middle Ages, Turkic languages were the main means of creating a rich literary heritage.

Famous works: Mahmud Kashgari - "Devonu lug'otit-turk", Yusuf Khos Hajib - "Kutadgu bilig", Ahmad Yugnakiy - "Hibat ul-haqoyiq".

Chigatai language and Alisher Navoi.

Chigatai language served as a common literary language for Turkic peoples in the Middle Ages.

Alisher Navoi's work demonstrated the cultural and literary power of Turkic languages.

"Khamsa" is the pride of the Turkic world and expresses the cultural values of the people (G. Akramov, 1997, 78-81).

Currently, literature written in Uzbek, Turkish, Kazakh, Azerbaijani and other languages is a continuation of the cultural wealth of Turkic languages.

Turkic languages are the main means of understanding national identity and transmitting cultural heritage to generations. Turkic languages play an important

role in uniting peoples living in different regions and strengthening their common values. Language preserves the historical and cultural memory of the people.

The musical art of the Turkic peoples was a tool for creating folk songs, epics and songs in the Turkic languages. For example, the Uzbek epic "Alpomish". Kazakh songs and tales "Koroglu". Examples of oral creativity of each Turkic people (fairy tales, proverbs, riddles) are a rich cultural heritage.

Turkic languages have played an important role in spreading Islam and developing its rich culture. Translations of the Quran and hadiths were made in the languages of the Turkic peoples.

Turkic languages are actively used today in cinema, theater and art. Popular Turkish TV series and films introduce Turkic languages to the world. Turkic languages are being promoted globally through today's modern technologies, social networks and content on the Internet.

Turkic languages are recognized by UNESCO as an integral part of cultural heritage. Although some small Turkic languages are under threat, special programs are being developed for their preservation. Turkic languages are actively used today in many countries of the world as state languages, official languages or languages of regional communication. Their development is closely related to technology, globalization, cultural integration and national policies. Also, although some Turkic languages are at risk of extinction, many efforts are being made internationally for their preservation and development.

Unfortunately, many Turkic languages, especially the languages of small peoples, are weakening under the influence of dominant languages (Russian, Chinese, English). At the same time, new lexical units, technological terms and global communication opportunities are developing in some languages. Turkic languages are actively supported as national languages in the countries of Central Asia. Some countries are transitioning to the Latin script, while others are aiming to revive historical writing systems.

Through the Turkic Cooperation Organization (TCTO), Turkic languages are undergoing a process of unification. Interlinguistic integration is developing through international events, festivals, and scientific conferences. Organizations such as UNESCO are implementing special programs to preserve endangered languages among the Turkic languages.

Problems and difficulties are mainly the threat of assimilation. Minor languages are often under the threat of assimilation by dominant languages (Russian, Chinese). Another sad aspect is the decreasing interest of the younger generation. Among young people, there is an increasing interest in learning international languages rather than their native language. In conclusion, it should be said that Turkic languages are one of the oldest and most widespread languages in the world, and their development and history are inextricably linked with the culture, politics and social life of peoples. Turkic languages are distinguished among the languages of the world by their rich history, lexical and grammatical features, as well as cultural and scientific significance. Their current state, distribution area and future depend on various political, economic and cultural processes, and comprehensive approaches are needed to preserve and develop Turkic languages. In the future, Turkic languages can further develop in the global arena and become an important tool for uniting different peoples. Today, Turkic languages are spoken by approximately 200 million people, which further increases their importance in the international arena. This language is a source of pride for the Turkic peoples. The preservation and development of Turkic languages is a task of not only national, but also global importance.

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